

REVIEW

Qualitative methodological approaches involving participants with intellectual disabilities: Scoping review of literature exploring death and dying

Marissa A Diaz¹ | Jerome E Bickenbach¹ | Carla Sabariego^{1,2,3} | Renaldo M Bernard¹

¹Swiss Paraplegic Research, Nottwil, Switzerland

²Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland

³Center for Rehabilitation in Global Health Systems, WHO Collaborating Center, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland

Correspondence

Marissa A Diaz, Swiss Paraplegic Research, Guido A. Zäch-Strasse 4 6207 Nottwil, Switzerland.

Email: marissa.diaz@stud.unilu.ch

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Abstract

Background: A paucity of qualitative research on sensitive topics that focuses on participants with intellectual disabilities leaves their views unexplored. This scoping review mainly aimed to provide an overview of qualitative data collection methods used in research involving participants with intellectual disabilities to explore death and dying.

Method: A scoping review of primary research and methodological papers published between January 2008 and March 2022 was conducted. The PRISMA-ScR checklist was followed.

Results: We identified 25 articles utilising four data collection methods: interviews, focus groups, the Nominal Group Technique, and participant observation. Data collection trends were identified, including accommodations for participants with intellectual disabilities, visual media used as a facilitator, and reporting of distress protocols. Most participants had mild to moderate intellectual disabilities.

Conclusions: The included studies demonstrate a flexible approach that relies on the use of multiple methods. Future research must adequately report study characteristics to ensure transparency and reliability.

KEYWORDS

death, end-of-life, intellectual disability, methodology, qualitative methods, research methods

1 | BACKGROUND

Qualitative research that investigates the views of people with intellectual disabilities is becoming increasingly common. The proliferation of research paradigms that situate people with disabilities as arbiters of knowledge production such as inclusive (Johnson & Walmsley, 2003) or participatory research (Chappell, 2000) amplify these marginalised voices. From a service delivery standpoint, there has been an increased interest in eliciting the voice of people with intellectual disabilities as service users (Perry, 2004). Policies and laws

should be informed by the lived experience of people with intellectual disabilities to ensure that their needs are being heard and met (Johnson, 2009). Despite these motivations, research involving participants with intellectual disabilities is not yet the norm.

There is a limited yet growing amount of research that includes this population. Qualitative studies involving participants with intellectual disabilities have been reported to be in the minority of published articles by three high-impact journals on intellectual disability—*Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, *American Journal of Intellectual and Developmental*

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Disabilities (Beail & Williams, 2014)—leaving these participants' perspectives largely unexplored in comparison to those of medical professionals and their caretakers and supporters. In comparison to the general population, this population's voice is comparatively rare to find in research, following a tradition that research tends to be *on* this population and not *with* them (Kiernan, 1999).

Understanding how to best conduct qualitative research that accommodates the needs of participants with intellectual disabilities is critical for their inclusion in research that concerns their lives. When participants have intellectual disabilities, researchers must overcome additional hurdles across multiple stages of the research. Various opinions regarding the potential harms to people with intellectual disabilities taking part in research studies might impede this population's participation due to attitudinal barriers, preventing such studies from gaining ethical approval (McDonald et al., 2008; McDonald et al., 2017). Perceptions about their ability to provide informed consent are also an attitudinal barrier (Calvey, 2012; McCarthy, 1998). Recruiting participants with intellectual disabilities is complex for various reasons, including engagement with family members and carers who may act as gatekeepers (Nicholson et al., 2013) and difficulties locating participants if they are unknown to service providers or not listed in a registry (Lennox et al., 2005). Planning the research involves collaboration with those close to participants or their service providers, who can provide both information on who would be interested in participating in the research project and how to best facilitate their contribution (Sigstad, 2014). Failing to account for the research needs of the population may introduce or reinforce barriers to participation (Hollomotz, 2018). Planning and implementing these accommodations often takes additional time and resources (Johnson & Walmsley, 2003).

It is additionally challenging to include participants with intellectual disabilities in research that explores sensitive topics, like death and dying. Researchers face two ethically and methodologically complex arenas—sensitive research and participants with intellectual disabilities—in a single research study (McCarthy, 1998). Adam et al. (2020) highlighted a lack of understanding of this population's palliative care needs due to having little research on the topic. In their systematic review focusing on the palliative care needs of this population and the barriers they encounter in accessing this care, only 1% of 2970 participants across the extracted studies had intellectual disabilities. Another literature review revealed a paucity of research on end-of-life decision-making that directly involves this population, resulting in a lack of evidence on how to best support them to ensure their rights (Kirkendall et al., 2017). These research gaps are especially egregious in light of their increasing life expectancy (Dolan et al., 2019). There is a great need to identify their support needs as they age (Bigby, 1997; Ryan & McQuillan, 2005), to overcome barriers to end-of-life care (Friedman et al., 2012), and to enhance end-of-life care provision in intellectual disability community services (Todd et al., 2020). In comparison with the general population, people with intellectual disabilities have worse health outcomes and tend to die at a younger age than those without intellectual disabilities (Awan & Chauhan, 2017), but they are often shielded from learning about their own deaths when they are ill (Kirkendall et al., 2017; McCarron et al., 2017; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2020) and left

out of bereavement and funeral rites (Raji et al., 2003). After concluding that people with intellectual disabilities are more likely to have complicated grief reactions, O'Riordan et al. (2022) recommended death education for this population. Considering the inevitability and universality of death, it is important that research acknowledges the voices of people with intellectual disabilities on a topic that will affect them, whether through their own deaths or the deaths of others.

There is some guidance available on how to overcome methodological challenges in conducting qualitative research with this population (Beail & Williams, 2014; Coons & Watson, 2013; D'Eath et al., 2005; Hollomotz, 2018; Nind, 2008; Sigstad, 2014; Sigstad & Garrels, 2018), but none specifically regarding sensitive topics like death and dying. It is important that research acknowledges the voices of people with intellectual disabilities on a topic that will inevitably affect them. This scoping review therefore aims to provide an overview of qualitative data collection methods used in research involving participants with intellectual disabilities to explore death and dying.

2 | METHOD

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Review (PRISMA-ScR) checklist guided this review (Tricco et al., 2018) and the Joanna Briggs Institute's guidance for scoping reviews (Khalil et al., 2021) was also used (Pollock et al., 2021). PRISMA recommendations have been widely endorsed across leading journals and systematic review initiatives and adopted across disciplines for its ability to support more complete reporting of systematic reviews (Page et al., 2021). PRISMA-ScR fits the needs of the study, specifically the aim to examine how research is conducted on a specific topic (Munn et al., 2018).

2.1 | Search strategy

MEDLINE, Scopus, CINAHL Complete (EBSCOhost), and PsycINFO bibliographic databases were searched. Search terms were based on concepts related to *intellectual disabilities*, *death and dying*, and *qualitative research* and are presented in Table A1. A hand search of journals across different disciplines with good impact factors (*The Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, *British Journal of Learning Disabilities*, *OMEGA: Journal of Death and Dying*, and *Palliative Medicine*) was conducted to locate publications that might be missed by the search of bibliographic databases (Teare & Taks, 2020). The reference lists of included publications were manually reviewed for eligible publications (Lockwood et al., 2019). Subject matter experts were asked to recommend relevant literature for consideration.

2.2 | Eligibility criteria

Included publications must describe qualitative research exploring the topic of death and dying involving participants with intellectual

disabilities, not proxies. Proxies are helpful resources when soliciting the views of people with severe or profound intellectual disabilities, but the aim of this review was to provide insight for engaging participants with intellectual disabilities from a methodological perspective. Therefore, our concepts for inclusion were *intellectual disabilities*, *death and dying*, and *qualitative research*. Beginning before adulthood, people with intellectual disabilities have difficulties with learning new skills and understanding new or abstract information (World Health Organisation, 2010). Qualitative research focuses on the collection and analysis of people's views, opinions, beliefs, and/or experiences (Carter & Little, 2007; Tavakol & Sandars, 2014a). Examples of qualitative research methods include focus groups, interviews, case studies, and ethnographic studies (Savage, 2006; Tavakol & Sandars, 2014b). Mixed methods studies were also included. For topics related to *death and dying*, topics related to healthcare (palliative care, terminal care, end-of-life care), but also those more abstract in nature (death, dying, bereavement, and suicide) were included to increase the breadth of the search. Primary studies and methodological papers in the English language and published between January 1st, 2008 and March 31st, 2022 were considered. Grey literature and books were omitted from the search to focus on peer-reviewed research and help ensure that the considered methods were reviewed and approved by an ethical board. Focusing on peer-review research also consolidated the resources of the research team and helped avoid publications that would not provide enough methodological details. Research based on the lived experience of people with disabilities is a legally-binding obligation put forward in Articles 4 and 12 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) (United Nations, 2006). Thus, the scope of this search aims to identify publications published the year the treaty came into force to the present.

2.3 | Eligibility assessment

Three disability rights researchers were involved in screening. They attended a training workshop to help ensure consistency in screening for this review, using an online service called Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016), without its artificial intelligence-based features. Each screener had a training set containing at least 25% of the total publications assigned for screening. Screeners were randomly assigned a set of titles and abstracts for initial screening, and afterwards full texts of the remaining records for final screening. A second screening of at least 20% was conducted. Screening was independently conducted to reduce the risk of reviewer bias and conflicting screening decisions (i.e., *include*, *maybe* or *exclude*) were resolved collaboratively.

2.4 | Data extraction and synthesis

MD extracted and synthesised the data. Data was extracted for general publication, participant, and data collection information. Specific data extraction labels are present in Table A1. Data extraction focused on methods used with participants with intellectual disabilities only.

For example, for the study from Tuffrey-Wijne et al. (2013) that collected data from people with intellectual disabilities through focus groups and from family carers and general health professionals with interviews, only the former was extracted for the purposes of this review. Proxies who have relationships with participants with intellectual disabilities could be a good resource given they know the participant well (Nind, 2008), but this comes with the risk that they may have difficulties separating their views from those of the person they are representing (Cummins, 2002). In mixed methods studies, the qualitative methods used and associated details were extracted.

Broad categories of methods—individual interviews, focus groups, participant observation, and Nominal Group Technique (NGT)—were used to organise the extracted data (Phillipson & Hammond, 2018). When mentioned, overarching methodological considerations, and specific methodological advantages and disadvantages were noted. Given the sensitivity of the topic and contested vulnerability of the population, any details about the planned response in the event of a participant becoming distressed were noted such as debriefing and providing details on support/counselling services (Kavanaugh & Ayres, 1998). Publications that described debriefing with participants (Hoover & Morrow, 2015) after data collection were noted since the focus of extraction was participant distress.

3 | RESULTS

A total of 25 publications were included in this scoping review. Figure 1 shows the PRISMA flowchart.

3.1 | Publication characteristics

The 25 included articles represent 23 studies. Five included papers (20%) (Cithambaram et al., 2019, 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010) reported on two studies. One methodological paper (Butler et al., 2012) reviewed two articles, with one article included in the review (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012) and one was not (Tuffrey-Wijne, 2013). Its contents were considered useful for extraction since it detailed focus group methods and included the perspectives of people with intellectual disabilities on collecting data. One study based in Hong Kong (Chow et al., 2017) replicated another study based in Ireland (McEvoy et al., 2012). Of the included papers, 52% originated from the UK, 24% from Ireland, and 8% from the Netherlands. Hong Kong, New Zealand, Pakistan, and Spain have one publication each.

Where mentioned (14/25, 56%), almost 50% (186/374) of the sample were women with ID. The year 2012 had the largest number of publications (4/25, 16%). Seventeen of the included studies (68%) reported levels of intellectual disabilities (see Table 1). Nine studies (53%) (Cithambaram et al., 2019, 2020; Cithambaram et al., 2021; Forrester-Jones, 2013; Haider & Zaman, 2022; McEvoy et al., 2012; McEvoy et al., 2017; Thorp et al., 2018; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013) collected data from people with mild to moderate disabilities and all

used interviews. Five studies (29%) (Chow et al., 2017; Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010) collected data from people with mild, moderate, and severe intellectual disabilities. One study (6%) (Young & Garrard, 2016) identified their participant as having profound intellectual disabilities.

3.2 | Characteristics of data collection methods

3.2.1 | Individual interviews

Seventeen of the included papers (68%) used individual interviews with people with intellectual disabilities in their studies. Most took place in Ireland (35%) or the UK (35%). All articles were published between 2012 and 2022, with most being published in 2012 (24%) and 2017 (18%). Two of these publications (Martean et al., 2013; Young & Garrard, 2016) used interviews in their case studies.

Where reported (10/17, 59%), duration of the interviews ranged from 15 to 90 min (Cithambaram et al., 2020; Cithambaram et al., 2021; Haider & Zaman, 2022; McEvoy et al., 2012; McEvoy et al., 2017; McKenzie et al., 2017; Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015; Ryan et al., 2012; Thorp et al., 2018; Voss et al., 2020). Only two studies reported interviews taking place over multiple days (Haider & Zaman, 2022; McRitchie et al., 2014). Settings of data collection was reported in eight of the 16 publications (50%) (Butler et al., 2012; Haider & Zaman, 2022; McEvoy et al., 2012; McEvoy et al., 2017; Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015; Ryan et al., 2012; Thorp et al., 2018; Voss et al., 2020) When specified, the settings of data collection were characterised as being “comfortable” (Thorp et al., 2018) or “quiet” (McEvoy et al., 2012; McEvoy et al., 2017; Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015). The choice of setting was explained in two studies (Ryan et al., 2012; Voss et al., 2020) and were reported as being chosen by the participants. Taking place during the COVID-19 pandemic, Haider and Zaman's (2022) study was conducted in separate rooms. Some studies (Haider & Zaman, 2022; Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015; Thorp et al., 2018) took place in the institutions that participated in the study.

Several studies described adjustments to the interview schedule to accommodate participants. Adjustments include modifying the number and type of questions (Cithambaram et al., 2021; Voss et al., 2020) and the shortening the length of the story based on the abilities of the participants (Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015). Participants who came into Voss et al.'s (2020) study with ideas to discuss were not told the prepared story since they did not need it to generate a discussion. Cithambaram et al. (2021) adjusted their interview guide based on information gathered from participants and discussed the interview guide with people with moderate intellectual disabilities before reading the book. Some participants could not relate to the topic of care at end-of-life due to their lack of experience with it and its intangibility (Cithambaram et al., 2019). Chow et al. (2017) note that in translating the tools from English used in McEvoy et al. (2012) there may be translation errors. Some combined interviews with other methods of data collection. One study used individual interviews to

include participants who could not attend focus groups (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012). Document reviews supplemented interviews in one study (McKenzie et al., 2017) to provide additional information on how the advanced care plan was documented, implemented, and shared. Interviews were one of many methods used in Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2012) study, which used NGT and focus groups to collect data over a period of four sessions. Four of these studies (Chow et al., 2017; McEvoy et al., 2012; McEvoy et al., 2017; Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015) used interviews alongside quantitative data collection in a mixed methods approach.

Many interview studies utilised visual media such as images to facilitate conversation. A reoccurring practice includes images shown alongside stories, such as a story of a person with incurable illness or a person learning that their relative is ill (Rodríguez Herrero et al., 2015; Voss et al., 2020). Pictures of body parts were used (McEvoy et al., 2017), as well as pictures of deceased family members (Ryan et al., 2012; Thorp et al., 2018). Cithambaram et al.'s (2021) study used a story from the book *Am I Going to Die?* (Hollins & Tuffrey-Wijne, 2009) to facilitate a discussion about care needs at end-of-life. Challenges were encountered in this study involving participants with intellectual disabilities becoming confused about the fictionality of the characters; researchers reminded them that the stories were fictional (Cithambaram et al., 2019). Video elicitation was used in one study (Young & Garrard, 2016).

3.2.2 | Focus groups

Six of the included papers (Butler et al., 2012; Forrester-Jones, 2013; McLaughlin et al., 2015; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013) used focus groups. One study (Reilly et al., 2020) held numerous group sessions with this population to teach them about death, so it was included in this section due to their general similarities. All these studies (Butler et al., 2012; Forrester-Jones, 2013; McLaughlin et al., 2015; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013) took place in the UK. All articles were published between 2012 and 2020, with four (67%) being published in 2012 alone.

Where reported (5/6, 83%) duration of the focus groups ranged from 30 to 180 min (Butler et al., 2012; Forrester-Jones, 2013; McLaughlin et al., 2015; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012). Forrester-Jones (2013) detailed the focus group schedule: 15 min for introductions, 45 min for the topic of funerals, 10 min for participant questions, and 20 min for winding down (for a total of 90 min). Most (5/6, 83%) described their studies as taking place over multiple different days (e.g. the same group meeting up again). One study (Forrester-Jones, 2013) reported to have met once, while the other studies met up three (Reilly et al., 2020) to four times (Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012). For accommodating online focus groups, Tuffrey-Wijne et al. (2013) reports that they lasted between three to 5 weeks, with one question being asked per week. The setting of where the focus groups took place was mentioned in five of the six publications (83%) (Butler et al., 2012; Forrester-

FIGURE 1 PRISMA flowchart of the review search, selection, and inclusion process.

Jones, 2013; McLaughlin et al., 2015; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012). Settings include day centres (Forrester-Jones, 2013; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012), an advocacy network office (McLaughlin et al., 2015) and a council building (Reilly et al., 2020). Reasons for the choice of setting range from privacy (Forrester-Jones, 2013) to familiarity to participants (Reilly et al., 2020) to convenience (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012).

Several studies described adjustments made to focus group schedules to accommodate participants. The two studies described in Butler et al. (2012) used ice breakers before data collection began. Some studies (Butler et al., 2012; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012) described sessions where participants chose what to focus on. Multiple data collection methods were used alongside focus groups, including roleplay (Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012), interviews (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012) and NGT (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012). Tuffrey-Wijne et al. (2012) supplemented their focus group with individual interviews for people who could not attend. One of the focus groups utilised semi-structured questionnaires based on previous interviews with intellectual disability service managers as a guide (Forrester-Jones, 2013). Participants created

documents focusing on what they want after death and completed an evaluation form after the third session in Reilly et al.'s (2020) study.

Images were used to facilitate focus groups in most of the publications. An image slide show depicting a man learning of his father's cancer diagnosis from *When Dad Died* (Hollins & Sireling, 1994) was shown to participants in Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2012) study. *Am I Going to Die?* (Hollins & Tuffrey-Wijne, 2009) was used in Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2013) study and participants were asked if the man in the story should be told about his prognosis. A similar approach was used in McLaughlin et al.'s (2015) study, which told the story of a dying woman with intellectual disabilities. PowerPoint slides were utilised during the second session in Reilly et al.'s (2020) study, which adapted a booklet titled *Let us Talk about Death* (Down Syndrome Scotland, 2013) to facilitate conversations around death and funerals. Participants repeatedly indicated that they did not like the imagery of a coffin to represent "Dead", so the researchers used an image of someone lying vertically. After the first session, participants were invited to bring something (e.g., photographs and booklets from funerals) that reminds them of someone who died that they want to discuss at the next session.

TABLE 1 Characteristics of included publications ($N = 25$).

Citation, country	Study aim	Data collection method(s)	Participants with intellectual disability (n), gender, reported level of intellectual disability	Participants without intellectual disability (n)
Bekkema et al. (2016); The Netherlands	To explore aspects of care relationships in end-of-life care from the perspectives of people with intellectual disabilities	Nominal group technique	33 (20 males, 13 females); Mild	0
Butler et al. (2012); England	To explore the execution of focus groups with people with intellectual disabilities that focused on cancer and breaking bad news	Focus groups, individual interviews, nominal group technique	6 (N/S); N/S	0
Chow et al. (2017); Hong Kong	To investigate people with intellectual disabilities' understanding of death concepts and to what extent	Individual interviews	110 (65 males, 45 females); Mild, moderate, severe	0
Cithambaram et al. (2019); Ireland	To explore the needs of people with intellectual disabilities with regards to end of life	Individual interviews	13 (N/S); Mild, moderate	0
Cithambaram et al. (2020); Ireland	To explore the perceptions of people with intellectual disabilities and families in terms of the information that is needed as part of end of life decision making	Individual interviews	11 (N/S); Mild, moderate	8
Cithambaram et al. (2021); Ireland	To find out the care needs of people with intellectual disabilities at the end of life in Ireland	Individual interviews	11 (N/S); Mild, moderate	8
Forrester-Jones (2013); England	To explore how practitioners deal with the topics of funerals and to investigate views of older people with and without intellectual disabilities on funerals	Focus groups, questionnaires	15 (9 males, 6 females); Mild, moderate	50
Haider & Zaman, 2022; Pakistan	To investigate adolescents with intellectual disabilities' experience with bereavement	Individual interviews	7 (N/S); Mild, moderate	0
Martean et al. (2013); England	To describe the experience of one woman with intellectual disabilities who has cancer	Individual interviews	1 (Female); N/S	0
McEvoy et al. (2012); Ireland	To explore how people with intellectual disabilities understand and explain death and make sense of life without the deceased	Individual interviews	34 (15 males, 19 females); Mild, moderate	0
McEvoy et al. (2017); Ireland	To explore the relationship between people with intellectual disabilities' biological knowledge and their understanding of the concept of death	Individual interviews	30 (16 males, 14 females); Mild, moderate	0
McKenzie et al. (2017); New Zealand	To explore the perspective of people with intellectual disabilities and life limiting conditions on the factors that strengthened and inhibited their Advanced Care Planning	Individual interviews, document reviews	4 (N/S); N/S	19
McLaughlin et al., 2015; Northern Ireland	To explore the views of people with intellectual disabilities and their family carers concerning palliative care	Focus groups	17 (5 males, 12 females); N/S	0
McRitchie et al. (2014); Scotland	To explore people with intellectual disabilities' lived experiences of bereavement	Individual interviews	13 (8 males, 5 females); Mild	0
Reilly et al. (2020); England	To describe the production and execution of a series of sessions delivered with an aim to educate people with intellectual disabilities about end of life	Questionnaires, group work	23 (8 males, 15 females); N/S	0
Rodríguez Herrero et al. (2015); Spain	To describe the concept of death among young people with intellectual disabilities	Individual interviews	75 (33 males, 42 females); Mild, moderate, severe	0
Ryan et al. (2012); Ireland	To investigate family life and loss from the perspective of people with intellectual disabilities who live in residential homes	Individual interviews	8 (N/S); N/S	0

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Citation, country	Study aim	Data collection method(s)	Participants with intellectual disability (n), gender, reported level of intellectual disability	Participants without intellectual disability (n)
Thorp et al. (2018); England	To explore the experience of bereavement for people with intellectual disabilities in a UK context	Individual interviews	4 (2 males, 2 females); Mild, moderate	0
Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, and Hollins (2010); England	To determine how much people with intellectual disabilities with cancer understand about their diagnosis and prognosis as well as how much they are told about their cancer	Participant observation, document reviews	13 (7 males, 6 females); Mild, moderate, severe	0
Tuffrey-Wijne et al. (2009); England	To provide insight into the experiences and needs of people with intellectual disabilities with cancer	Participant observation	13 (N/S); Mild, moderate, severe	0
Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al. (2010); England	To investigate the experiences of people with intellectual disabilities with cancer	Participant observation	13 (N/S); Mild, moderate, severe	0
Tuffrey-Wijne et al. (2012); England	To explore the experiences of people with intellectual disabilities who have a relative or friend with cancer and to identify their support needs	Focus groups, individual interviews, nominal group technique	21 (N/S); N/S	0
Tuffrey-Wijne et al. (2013); England	To develop guidelines for decisions about (non-)disclosure of bad news around life-limiting illness and death to people with intellectual disabilities	Focus groups, nominal group technique	21 (N/S); Mild, moderate	88
Voss et al. (2020); The Netherlands	To explore what is important for advance care planning for people with intellectual disabilities in the palliative phase	Individual interviews	5 (2 males, 3 females); N/S	15
Young and Garrard (2016); Scotland	To explore how the use of a memory box supported the bereavement process of a woman with intellectual disabilities	Individual interviews	1 (Female); Profound	3

3.2.3 | Participant observation

Three of the included papers (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010) described participant observation in an ethnographic study focusing on ascertaining the needs of people who have intellectual disabilities and cancer. Thirteen participants with mild to severe intellectual disabilities were observed in various locations with and outside of their homes (e.g., day centres, hospitals, and outpatient settings) (Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010). All participants had cancer and 10 were terminally ill. At the time of diagnosis, seven participants lived in staffed residential care homes, four in their own apartments, one in their parents' home, and one with foster carers (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009). Two hundred and fifty hours were spent with participants, often weekly, during a median time range of seven months (Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010). Field notes were kept by researchers, including descriptions of conversations and observations and others involved such as social care staff, medical staff, and relatives were spoken to (Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010). There is no mention of extended discussions with participants with ID within the three included articles.

3.2.4 | Nominal group technique

Four of the included papers (Bekkema et al., 2016; Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013) used NGT with participants with intellectual disabilities. Three of the studies (75%) originated in the UK and one (25%) in the Netherlands. The articles were published between 2012 and 2016, with two reporting on the same study being published in 2012 (Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012).

Where noted (3/4, 75%), the NGT lasted 60 min (Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013) and all met multiple times. Bekkema et al.'s (2016) study took place over two sessions with two to 3 weeks between. As described, two articles (Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012) noted having focus groups four times, with weeks or months between. The location of the focus groups was noted in three of the four publications (75%) (Bekkema et al., 2016; Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012) and all locations were familiar to participants. Bekkema et al. (2016) characterised the familiar location where groups met as "safe" whereas Butler et al. (2012) detailed the convenience of meeting where the disability charities and independent day centres they recruited from having a set meeting place.

NGT was a supplementary method, always used to rank ideas presented in a previous session of data collection. As NGT relies on voting, each study's application of the method focused on ascertaining the participants' views. Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2012) study used NGT in the last of four sessions to rank participants' ideas. Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2013) study noted that NGT was used to rank statements made during the group sessions without detailing the actual statements. Bekkema et al. (2016) used NGT in the latter of two sessions by organising ideas from the first session and having participants vote on those ideas in the second session.

With regards to NGT, three of the studies (Bekkema et al., 2016; Butler et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012) described using images to illustrate ideas for participants to vote on. Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2012) study used images from the Books Beyond Words series to convey ideas formulated by participants in the previous sessions. Similarly, Bekkema et al.'s (2016) study illustrated ideas generated in the previous session and put them on cards, although they do not describe what the images themselves look like. Butler et al. (2012) describes illustrating the ideas generated, but also does not describe the images. Participants in the group interviews in Bekkema et al. (2016) were asked to think about what would be the best care for a woman with incurable illness after being told her story. The group afterwards discussed the generated ideas. It was after this session that NGT was used in the following session.

3.2.5 | Distress protocols

Multiple strategies to alleviate distress in participants are presented across most publications (20/25, 80%). Before data collection, some articles report consulting with advisory groups that guided studies along the course of research (Forrester-Jones, 2013; McKenzie et al., 2017; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010). During data collection, some studies provided counselling and support services in the case of distress (Bekkema et al., 2016; Cithambaram et al., 2019, 2020; Cithambaram et al., 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2015; Thorp et al., 2018; Voss et al., 2020) and seven papers (Bekkema et al., 2016; Butler et al., 2012; Chow et al., 2017; Forrester-Jones, 2013; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2013) reported that staff members, familiar to the participants, were present without reporting if this helped relieve distress. After data collection, some studies followed up with the participants or their supporters (Cithambaram et al., 2019; Forrester-Jones, 2013; McEvoy et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010). Other studies held debriefing sessions with participants (Forrester-Jones, 2013; McLaughlin et al., 2015).

4 | DISCUSSION

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first scoping review to focus on methods used in qualitative research involving participants with

intellectual disabilities on topics related to death and dying. Twenty-five articles reporting on 23 studies were included. While various regions are represented, there is no representation from North or South America. Considering that the United States, which never ratified the CRPD (Kanter, 2020), has an estimated 7.43 million people with intellectual disabilities (Residential Information Systems Project, 2018), this research gap has implications regarding American research priorities. This review identified several data collection trends, including adjustments to accommodate participants with intellectual disabilities, visual media being used as a facilitator, and the reporting of distress protocols. In providing details on the included publications, this scoping review can serve as a guide to researchers who are interested in the topic and policymakers who want to know how researchers are qualitatively capturing this population's views, beliefs, and opinions on topics related to death and dying.

This review complements the existing literature on qualitative research with persons with intellectual disabilities and elaborates on a sensitive research topic, namely death and dying. Coons and Watson (2013) described the general ethical and practical challenges of qualitative research with this population while Beail and Williams (2014) reviewed qualitative methods used with this population across three major intellectual disability journals over a decade. Results of this scoping review are generally in line with their findings. Some practical accommodations mentioned in Coons and Watson's (2013) review, such as the use of visual media and flexibility of methods, are in line with this review. The review from Beail and Williams (2014) mentioned that some of the included articles not only failed to report important sample characteristics such as the sample size, but also noted that some of the studies failed to detail the interview schedule. Challenges in conducting end-of-life research with adults with intellectual and developmental disabilities were detailed in Savage et al.'s (2015) study. The findings of this review align with theirs, especially the focus on distress and expands the scope to include other data collection methods. Other publication types detailing work reported by the included studies, such as grey literature and books, may exist and could be useful for gaining methodological insight. For example, *Living with Learning Disabilities, Dying with Cancer: Thirteen Personal Stories* (Tuffrey-Wijne, 2010) which is based on three of the included studies (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010), could inform the planning of methods by deepening ones' understanding of participants' experiences.

4.1 | Accommodations for studies involving participants with intellectual disabilities

Qualitative methodologies require a range of accommodations when participants have intellectual disabilities. When it comes to participants who can communicate verbally, there is evidence that adjustments must be made to accommodate the needs and preferences of this population in qualitative research. For instance, Finlay and Lyons (2002) reported that this population tends to acquiesce. McEvoy et al.'s (2012) study explicitly used a semi-structured format to avoid

acquiesce and other challenges. However, Hollomotz (2018) used yes/no questions in their interview schedule and checked answers by reframing the question (McCarthy, 1998). This is in line with Sigstad's (2014) study, which utilised repetition to confirm what was already said and get more information from participants with intellectual disabilities. They concluded that researchers must be prepared to follow up open questions with questions that are more specific if the participant misunderstands. People with intellectual disabilities are not a homogenous group and their challenges and preferences vary and a "one-sized fits all" approach to conducting research will not succeed. As this research is rare, guidance to overcome the challenges posed by research involving participants with intellectual disabilities will increase the number of academics conducting such studies. Formal guidance will also be useful for researchers who wish to engage in topics that may be potentially distressing for participants and subject to rigorous ethical approval. However, any formal guidance should delineate methods that are appropriate for a range of impairments while also allowing room for flexibility in methods.

4.2 | Flexibility in data collection methods

Flexibility in research involving participants with intellectual disabilities requires creativity and an inclusive approach to data collection (Corby et al., 2018). The variety of communication styles in this population necessitate a flexible approach to the interview guide (Hollomotz, 2018). Flexibility was seen in studies that took place over multiple sessions, focusing on what participants indicated they wanted to focus on (Butler et al., 2012; Reilly et al., 2020; Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2012). This is also exemplified in a study (Tuffrey-Wijne & Davies, 2007) reporting on preliminary findings from a study across three articles (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010), where a single participant from the ethnographic study spoke about his experience with the first author across a five-month period. Sigstad and Garrels (2018) point out that validity and reliability may be put at risk when adopting a flexible approach to research focusing on this population, and they suggest different methods to ensure the integrity of the study, namely using the same vocabulary as the participants during data collection and spending more time with them to know their communication styles better. Researchers who take a flexible approach must be trained in various communication and data collection methods. Researchers need time to use multiple methods to achieve validity and reliability.

Considering COVID-19, the timing of this scoping review (and the extracted articles) is situated within a largely offline context. There is a growing amount of research with this population that explores their experiences online during the pandemic (Power et al., 2021). Researchers could follow the flexible approach of Tuffrey-Wijne et al.'s (2013) study, where participants were invited to respond at their convenience, with all the answers being sent by email to the entire focus group so other participants could respond. However, there are several barriers faced by this population in accessing the

internet including financial barriers, societal attitudes, education and training barriers, and individual impairment issues (Chadwick et al., 2013). As researchers translate data collection online, it is imperative that they consider the needs of the population and produce qualitative research that is both valid and reliable without introducing additional barriers.

4.3 | Using visual media as a communication tool

Images and videos are often more accessible to those with intellectual disabilities and so the use of visual media in research is important in discovering information about their lives (Boxall & Ralph, 2009). The use of photos alongside interviews have been shown to facilitate interviews with this population, serving as a jumping-off point for conversations (Folkestad, 2000), and this is largely in-line with the results of this study, where images were often used in interviews and focus groups. The use of images to facilitate communication with this population has been investigated and suggested across disciplines, including health care (Ziviani et al., 2004) and assisted technology (Robertson et al., 2021). However, it is unclear how much the use of images assist methods like Easy Read and what type of images are best understood by people with intellectual disabilities (Sutherland & Isherwood, 2016). While the use of images alongside methods like interviews and focus groups may facilitate data collection, some participants with profound impairments are still unable to participate in studies that use these methods, regardless of the amount of images used (Nind, 2008). Researchers must be mindful of the use of visual methods on two fronts; they must use appropriate images in line with the goals of the study while also acknowledging that some participants may not be able to participate in a focus group or interview study despite the use of visual media.

4.4 | Inclusion of people with severe to profound intellectual disabilities

When considering accommodations made across the included studies in this review, it is important to consider that most of the primary research studies identified collected data from people with mild to moderate disabilities. This has been identified as an issue in research with this population; people with intellectual disabilities are not a homogenous group (Roll, 2018) and research must be adjusted to reflect this and include participants with a range of cognitive impairments and communication preferences. People with severe or profound intellectual disabilities may require proxies to participate in research since their impairments complicate participation (Bigby et al., 2014), but methods that rely on elicitation to visual prompts can include this population since they do not rely solely on verbal articulation (Cluley, 2017). Elicitation methods use written materials, videos, or photos including the participants to prompt recollection and facilitate reflection from the participants about the subject or experience depicted (Henry & Fetters, 2012). Photovoice is a participatory

elicitation method where the participants take photos that are later used to facilitate discussions about the content of the photos themselves, thus situating the participants as part of the analysis as well (Overmars-Marx et al., 2018; Wang & Burris, 1997). The one study that used such a method (Young & Garrard, 2016) was also the only study with a participant with profound intellectual disabilities. Without the proliferation of qualitative methods that rely on visual media for data collection, people with severe and profound intellectual disabilities will continue to be excluded from research studies. While there is arguably tension between employing unorthodox methods of data collection and maintaining structured academic standards, methods like Photovoice can broaden the tools of qualitative research and gather more information about this population's lives (Aldridge, 2007; Boxall & Ralph, 2009). To have a complete understanding of this population's views and not leave out participants with severe or profound intellectual disabilities, researchers must be trained not only in qualitative methods that use visual media, but also in the practice of photography and/or videography to assist participants.

4.5 | Distress protocols

Distress protocols are especially relevant in qualitative studies talking about end-of-life with participants with intellectual disabilities. To uncover strategies that mitigate stress and distress, it is important that measures taken in research studies dealing with sensitive topics are not only described but justified. Ethics boards often require assessments of the potential risk to participants and a plan detailing how risk and accompanying distress will be mitigating during the research study (Guest et al., 2013). Especially in studies on sensitive issues, it is important for researchers to be prepared for distress and be able to determine when the research is too upsetting for the participant to continue. Most included studies mentioned plans to mitigate distress or how distress was dealt with when it arose. Stancliffe et al. (2021), in a paper investigating if talking about end-of-life with adults with intellectual disabilities caused psychological harm, mentioned that distress was identified in various studies that were extracted for this article (Cithambaram et al., 2019; Forrester-Jones, 2013; McEvoy et al., 2012; McEvoy et al., 2017) but noted that none of the studies described that participants were affected by distress or the degree of said distress. While it is unrealistic to provide a universal guidance for ethical approval since ethics boards have different requirements, it is important that researchers report on distress protocols used in their studies to serve as an example for other researchers who want to do similar work.

4.6 | Inadequate reporting

The lack of formal methodological guidance on conducting research on sensitive topics with persons with intellectual disabilities is reflected in the unsystematic and non-standardised reporting of study characteristics and methodology. Reporting on the participants' level

of intellectual disabilities is likely to continue to differ between studies due to theoretical differences between academic disciplines and epistemological viewpoints between researchers. Disability studies researchers have argued that the label of intellectual disability is ambiguous and socially constructed (Bjornsdottir, 2010; Williams et al., 2015). Due to these variety of perspectives on the use of labels in intellectual disabilities, it is even more important for research studies with this population as participants to be clear about other aspects of its study characteristics and methodology and follow general guidelines such as those proposed by Koch et al. (2014) or frameworks such as the Standards for Reporting Qualitative Research (SRQR) (O'Brien et al., 2014) and the Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research (COREQ) (Tong et al., 2007).

4.7 | Limitations of the review

One researcher (MD) completed data extraction and synthesis but extracted data was reviewed a second time after several days to help improve the accuracy and reliability of extraction. This scoping review limited results to English, perhaps resulting in the very few studies from Asia and none from Africa or South America. However, given there are no results from North America, perhaps this is more indicative of research priorities on this continent. Future scoping reviews can include other languages. Unanticipated poor reporting from the extracted articles pre-empted our decision to exclude grey literature and books but our preliminary search results revealed no otherwise eligible publications. The eligibility criteria for study participants can be perceived as strict, but it still accommodates studies using proxies to supplement direct feedback from people with severe or profound intellectual disabilities. For example, Young and Garrard's (2016) study focused the discussion with the participant with intellectual disabilities and her family, including the participant's vocalisations. Save for one article by Tuffrey-Wijne and Davies (2007), known to us, it was not anticipated that other relevant articles, as suggested by our preliminary searches and our hand search of reference lists, would have been published before our publication date restriction in 2008. Tuffrey-Wijne and Davies (2007) provided minute methodological detail for a study that was further detailed in three of the included articles (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2009; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, & Hollins, 2010; Tuffrey-Wijne, Bernal, Hubert, et al., 2010). Another otherwise eligible article (Gilrane-McGarry & Taggart, 2007) was published 1 year before the date restriction. We do not believe many others, if any, would have been published before the publication date restriction. Another article (Tuffrey-Wijne et al., 2008), while focusing on ethical and methodological considerations of doing research on cancer, death, and dying with people with learning disabilities, was not included due to its lack of focus on data collection methods.

5 | CONCLUSION

Our scoping review reports on methods that have been used in qualitative research exploring death and dying and involving participants

with intellectual disabilities. There are many methodological approaches to conducting research with this population and there is no singular approach that will accommodate the needs of every participant. This review serves as a reference for researchers who explore sensitive topics with this population with an aim to conduct thorough and well-reported research. Future research should consider more inclusive methods, for example that accommodate more participants with severe and profound intellectual disabilities, in sensitive topics.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

ORCID

Renaldo M Bernard <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6958-3369>

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APPENDIX

TABLE A1 Search terms.

Natural language: PubMed	intellectual disabilit*[Title/Abstract] OR learning disabilit*[Title/Abstract] OR intellectual development disorder*[Title/Abstract] OR "mental retardation"[Title/Abstract] OR "developmentally delayed"[Title/Abstract]	death[Title/Abstract] OR dying[Title/Abstract] OR "end of life"[Title/Abstract] OR "end-of-life"[Title/Abstract] OR "palliative care"[Title/Abstract] OR "terminal care"[Title/Abstract] OR suicide[Title/Abstract]	qualitative[Title/Abstract] OR "grounded theory"[Title/Abstract] OR interview*[Title/Abstract] OR ethnograph*[Title/Abstract] OR observation*[Title/Abstract] OR focus group*[Title/Abstract]
Mesh: PubMed	Intellectual Disability[Mesh] OR Learning Disabilities[Mesh]	Palliative Care[Mesh] OR Terminal Care [Mesh] OR Suicide[Mesh] OR Hospice Care[Mesh]	Qualitative Research[Mesh] OR Focus Groups[Mesh] OR Grounded Theory [Mesh]
Full query: PubMed	intellectual disabilit*[Title/Abstract] OR learning disabilit*[Title/Abstract] OR intellectual development disorder*[Title/Abstract] OR "mental retardation"[Title/Abstract] OR "developmentally delayed"[Title/Abstract] OR Intellectual Disability [Mesh] OR Learning Disabilities [Mesh]	death[Title/Abstract] OR dying[Title/Abstract] OR "end of life"[Title/Abstract] OR "end-of-life"[Title/Abstract] OR "palliative care"[Title/Abstract] OR "terminal care"[Title/Abstract] OR suicide[Title/Abstract] OR Palliative Care[Mesh] OR Terminal Care[Mesh] OR Suicide [Mesh] OR Hospice Care[Mesh]	qualitative[Title/Abstract] OR "grounded theory"[Title/Abstract] OR interview*[Title/Abstract] OR ethnograph*[Title/Abstract] OR observation*[Title/Abstract] OR focus group*[Title/Abstract] OR Qualitative Research[Mesh] OR Focus Groups[Mesh] OR Grounded Theory[Mesh]
Full query: ProQuest (syntax)	"intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual development disorder*" OR "mental retardation" OR "developmentally delayed" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit"	death OR dying OR "end of life" OR "end-of-life" OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "hospice care"	qualitative OR "grounded theory" OR interview* OR ethnograph* OR observation* OR "focus group*" OR "qualitative research" OR "focus group*" OR "grounded theory"
Full query: ProQuest	(ti("intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual development disorder*" OR "mental retardation" OR "developmentally delayed" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit") OR ab("intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual development disorder*" OR "mental retardation" OR "developmentally delayed" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit") OR MAINSUBJECT("intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual development disorder*" OR "mental retardation" OR "developmentally delayed" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR "learning disabilit"))	(ti(death OR dying OR "end of life" OR "end-of-life" OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "palliative care" OR "hospice care") OR ab(death OR dying OR "end of life" OR "end-of-life" OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "hospice care") OR MAINSUBJECT(death OR dying OR "end of life" OR "end-of-life" OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR "hospice care"))	(ti(qualitative OR "grounded theory" OR interview* OR ethnograph* OR observation* OR "focus group*" OR "qualitative research" OR "focus group*" OR "grounded theory") OR ab(qualitative OR "grounded theory" OR interview* OR ethnograph* OR observation* OR "focus group*" OR "qualitative research" OR "focus group*" OR "grounded theory") OR MAINSUBJECT(qualitative OR "grounded theory" OR interview* OR ethnograph* OR observation* OR "focus group*" OR "qualitative research" OR "focus group*" OR "grounded theory"))
Full query: Scopus	intellectual disabilit* OR learning disabilit* OR intellectual development disorder* OR "mental retardation" OR "developmentally delayed" OR Intellectual Disability OR Learning Disabilities	death OR dying OR "end of life" OR "end-of-life" OR "palliative care" OR "terminal care" OR suicide OR Palliative Care OR Terminal Care OR Suicide OR Hospice Care	qualitative OR "grounded theory" OR interview* OR ethnograph* OR observation* OR focus group* OR Qualitative Research OR Focus Groups OR Grounded Theory